

PROTOTYPE OF OPEN PRECISION IRRIGATION / FERTIGATION TOOLS AND SYSTEMS AND PROTOCOL FOR THE IMPLEMENTATION

D5.5

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Short Description
<p>This documentation forms the basis for the realization, implementation and management of the project prototype precision irrigation system. The objective is to propose a technological solution for the optimal management of irrigation using precision farming tools in order to save water consumption of market garden crops (potatoes, onions and carrots) without reducing the quantity and quality of production. It includes the prototype objectives, general considerations and recommendations together with the following two sections:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the prototype section that provides a scientific-technological description of the R&I process carried out to realize the prototype (final innovative method / system / tool / product) as result of the testing phase in lab / at small-scale level (WP4) and feedback gathered from the in-field validation (WP5). According to the impact pathway approach, it describes the conducted activities, the reached outputs and outcomes, and the obtained measures of relevant key performance indicators demonstrating the impact; - the protocol section that adopts an operational perspective to describe how to implement and manage the prototype, thus ensuring its full functionality and usability. It includes deployment requirements, procedures, methods, techniques, and practical considerations. Moreover, the protocols generate guidelines (D4.X), practice abstracts (D6.5) and training materials (D5.1).

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Abbreviations and glossary

Abbreviation/ specialist term	Explanation
IoT	Internet of Things, referring to interconnected devices for data collection
LoRaWAN	Long Range Wide Area Network
ETc	Crop Evapotranspiration
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization
RCT	Randomized Control Trials
Kc	Crop coefficient to estimate crop water requirements.
GGP	Green Generation Program
SIAM	International Agricultural Show of Morocco
ANRT	National Telecommunications Regulatory Agency
API	Application Programming Interface
DBAC	Completely Randomized Block Design
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
RAW	Readily Available Water.
RCBD	Randomized Complete Block Design
SMS	Short Message Service
MA	Morocco

Descriptions should be concise and schematic and may be integrated with figures, flowcharts, schemes, diagrams, ... where relevant.

From this deliverable the following operational documents aiming at providing adopters with practical information will be derived by the end of February:

- *D4.X – Guidelines (updating the ones already produced);*
- *D6.5 – One-page practice abstract;*
- *D5.1 – Training materials (updating the ones already produced).*

1. Background

1.1 Prototype motivations and objectives

Problem(s) the (open) prototype aims to solve or the user needs intends to address, concept, specific objectives and targets (with special attention to gender issues).

Agriculture in sub-Saharan countries such as Uganda is largely dependent on rainfall. In many regions, this limits the growing season to the annual rainy season. Anthropogenic climate change is affecting the reliability of wet and dry season patterns and threatening food security. A precision irrigation system was developed using affordable and readily available materials to improve the effectiveness and resilience of smallholder food production.

Specifically, recent studies in the Saïs plain have revealed that the dominance of over-irrigation, with parcel-based irrigation efficiencies between 15% and 90%. Indeed, in the absence of constraints on the resource and because of its relative low cost, farmers prefer to bring excess water in order to avoid any stress and potential yield losses. Thus, used to gravity irrigation, they irrigate by drip until water visibly accumulates in the basins. This results in significant losses of resources and implies a low level of technical knowledge in irrigation management in general.

The objective is to propose a technological solution for the optimal management of irrigation using precision agriculture tools in order to save water consumption of market garden crops (potatoes, onions and carrots) without reducing the quantity and quality of production.

The goal is to help local farmers and small farmers to be more proactive in the field, not only by reducing water consumption, but also by improving crop health and production.

Field trials were conducted to validate the scientific algorithm integrated into the application for calculating optimal irrigation doses.

The implementation of a digital solution allowing small farmers to program irrigation based on continuous monitoring of the soil and plant climate using sensors and a smartphone application. All information is collected using data from

sensors installed in the field and irrigation recommendations are disseminated through a dedicated mobile application.

With agricultural IoT sensors installed in field monitoring stations, small farmers can have a powerful dashboard with analytics capabilities and built-in drip irrigation monitoring features.

2. Prototype

This section provides a scientific-technological description of the R&I process carried out to realize the prototype (final new method / system / tool / product) as result of the testing phase in lab / at small-scale level (WP4) and feedback gathered from the field innovation validation (WP5).

According to the impact pathway approach (in line with D4.12 focused on WP4), it describes the conducted activities, the reached outputs and outcomes, and the measurement of relevant key performance indicators demonstrating the impact.

Food Hub	Food Product
Ait Ouallal Bittit/Ait Yazem (MA)	Fresh vegetables (onions, potatoes, carrots)
Nakaseke (UG)	Fresh vegetables (leaf vegetables, tomatoes)

2.1 Summary of the R&I activities: from testing to validating

Brief description of the scientific-technological criteria and R&I path (development, test, and validation) for the realization of the innovative technology / system / process / tool.

Nakaseke (UG)

The development of the precision irrigation system was guided by the need to identify key criteria for its successful adoption in a small-scale farming context in Uganda. Initial activities included a comprehensive literature review and farm visits across the country to understand the challenges faced by local farmers. These investigations highlighted that affordability, robustness to environmental conditions and infrastructure failures, and material availability were critical factors for a successful system design.

In the field trials, various the precision irrigation components and commercially available solutions including watermark and chameleon soil moisture sensors and LoRa radio were tested to evaluate the performance under real-world conditions. These trials focused on assessing the system's ability to manage water usage and optimize crop yields in tomato cultivation.

As a follow-up, more cost-effective technical solutions were explored to refine and optimize the system. This included testing alternative hardware and software

configurations, ultimately leading to the development of the final precision irrigation system, which is better suited for the resource constraints and environmental conditions of smallholder farms in Uganda.

Ait Ouallal Bittit/Ait Yazem (MA)

The entire system integrate data from weather stations, field sensors and historical data on crop needs and yields to produce highly accurate forecasts of irrigation rates and frequencies. Models adapted to the different types of soils make it possible to adapt the recommended water supplies, thus improving the predictive accuracy of the system.

The tasks focus on four main pillars namely:

1. Conduct agronomic experimentation on deficit irrigation and on the development of irrigation scheduling parameters for specific crops
2. Development and implementation of a solution for parcel-based irrigation consulting using precision farming tools and a mobile application on smart phones,
3. Support and training of farmers on the installation, maintenance of sensors and use of the mobile application designed for irrigation reasoning at the field level; (RCTs)
4. Setting up a demonstration trials in best precision irrigations practices for fresh vegetables. (Dissemination in ENAM Demonstration Unit – Experimental Farm)

Figure 1: Conceptual design of the precision agriculture irrigation connectivity model

2.1.1 Irrigation Trials

a. Potatoes

The plant material used for this study is potato (*Solanum tuberosum*) of the 'desirée' variety imported from the Netherlands. Seeding was carried out in the field at a depth of 10 cm, on rows spaced at 80 cm apart and 30 cm tuber spacing.

The experimental design adopted is a complete randomized block design (DBAC), with a single source of heterogeneity with four repetitions and three water regimes. The three water regimes are as follows:

- Control T1: is a comfort irrigation with 100% crop evapotranspiration ET_c throughout the whole cycle;
- Treatment T2: corresponds to sustainable deficit irrigation with an application of 75% ET_c during the whole cycle; (i.e., a 25% of water restriction).
- Treatment T3: sustainable deficit irrigation with 50% ET_c applied throughout the cycle; (i.e., 50% of water restriction).

A localized irrigation was provided by a drip system, including drippers each supplying 1.6 l/h, spaced at a distance of 0.4 m from each other.

As this study focused on water supply, the crop was conducted in a non-limiting manner concerning the other factors (tillage, density, fertilization, weeding, etc.)

b. Onion

This trial addressed onion crop responses to continuous deficit irrigation with triggering thresholds of readily available water content. The experiment was conducted on an experimental plot in open field. Three water regimes were applied T1 control (100%), T2 (75%) and T3 (50%) of crop evapotranspiration ET_c combined with two triggering thresholds (10% and 5%). This is a complete random block device with four repetitions.

The measurements concerned the monitoring of vegetative, eco-physiological and yield parameters.

c. Carrots

In the present study, five treatments were implemented with only one factor considered (crop evapotranspiration "ET_c") and an additional 6th treatment to model K_c. It should be mentioned that all treatments received 100% irrigation from transplanting to the one leaf stage. The treatments are as follows:

- Treatment T1: Luxury irrigation with a dose of 125% ET_c from the one-leaf stage;
- Treatment T2: Comfort irrigation with 100% ET_c throughout the cycle;

- Treatment T3: Continuous deficit irrigation with an application of 85% ET_c from the one-leaf stage;
- Treatment T4: Continuous deficit irrigation with an application of 75% ET_c from the one leaf stage;
- Treatment T5: Continuous deficit irrigation with an application of 66% ET_c from the one-leaf stage;
- The 6th treatment concerns the monitoring of the K_c with water probes in order to adjust the K_c of the FAO to accommodate the Saïs area.

The study was conducted using a randomized complete block design (RCBD), with one source of heterogeneity being the gradient and 4 repetitions

2.1.2 Smart irrigation system

The objective is to develop a specific decision-making platform that offers local farmers effective solutions for sustainable irrigation management and based on standard wireless IoT technology under LoRaWAN.

Using the soil moisture probes and the weather station, recommended irrigation doses are calculated based on the climate situation (meteorological data) and in relation to plot data on soil moisture and crop needs depending on their stage of development.

In order to disseminate technological innovation to small farmers who cannot afford to buy capacitive probes connected to the local LoRaWAN network, it is possible to provide useful and precise information on the irrigation doses to recommend for each crop according to the stages of development in the entire community of farmers based on information from their neighborhood by type of crop and according to the stages of development throughout the community of farmers using the mobile application (without any cost).

2.2 Summary of the outputs

2.2.1 Results and achievements

Short description of the new technologies / systems / processes / tools.

Nakaseke (UG)

In alignment with the principles of affordability and accessibility, the components for the system were selected based on their low cost and availability, either through international delivery or local sourcing in Uganda. To ensure independence from internet infrastructure, a local processing approach was adopted. The system includes battery backups to mitigate the effects of power outages. An overview of the proposed smart irrigation system is illustrated in

Figure 1. The system features a proposed sensor node positioned at the field level, which connects common soil moisture sensors, such as the commercial Watermark sensor [WATERMARK 200SS, Irrrometer Company, Riverside, USA] or the more cost-effective Chameleon sensors [Chameleon Sensor Array, VIA Ltd, Melbourne, Australia], to an enclosed LoRa module consisting of an interface module [SMX, EME Systems, Berkeley, USA], a microcontroller [HUZZAH32, Adafruit Industries, New York, USA] and a LoRa transmitter [E220-900T22D LoRa Wireless UART Module, Ebyte, China]. These components are powered by a waterproof battery and solar panel [EESBAO-35W, Shenzhen Tengyunfei Technology Co., Shenzhen City, China]. An alternative commercial sensor node is the KIWI solution [KIWI agriculture sensor, TEKTELIC, Calgary, Canada], that also connects to a watermark sensor and in addition to the soil moisture collects also humidity, temperature and light intensity data. The collected data is transmitted to a LoRa gateway unit, which is typically located in an office, farmer's house, or community center.

At the core of the gateway unit is a microcontroller [Raspberry Pi 4B, Raspberry Pi Ltd, Cambridge, United Kingdom], which is connected to a LoRa concentrator board [GPMLx9332-PX V3, Greenpalm, Hangzhou, China] and a 5-dB antenna. The gateway operates on open-source software [Chirpstack V4, Orne Brocaar, Amsterdam, The Netherlands], which includes network and application server functionality. To safeguard against power interruptions, a small uninterruptible power supply [UPS Module 3s, Waveshare, Shenzhen, China] is integrated into the system. When irrigation is required, a command is sent to activate a wireless motorized shut-off smart valve [STREGA, Ohain, Belgium] that is programmed to open for a specific period depending on the soil's antecedent soil moisture and its field capacity. The valve is set to operate as a Class A LoRa device.

Figure 2: Design overview of the developed LoRa Smart irrigation system

Ait Ouallal Bittit/Ait Yazem (MA)

a. Experimental Trials

Validation of the models for calculating the water requirements of vegetable crops based on the results of trials carried out in 2020 and 2022 (Kc) with a view to reducing crop water inputs.

For potatoes trails, the highest marketable tuber yield was recorded by the T1 treatment (dose =100% ETc) which is 42.51 Tones/ha, and the lowest yield was that recorded by the T3 treatment (dose =50%) which is 20.96 Tones/ha. Analysis of variance showed a highly significant effect of irrigation rate on final potato yield. Treatment T2 (dose=75%) gave almost equal yield (41.17 T/ha) to control T1 (dose=100%), but a 50% restriction of ETc resulted in a 49% yield loss. The effect of applying a water restriction of about 25% compared to comfort irrigation (100% ETc) resulted in water savings of about 77mm while maintaining a high yield. In fact, the good water use efficiency was recorded in the plants irrigated at 75% of the crop water requirements.

It is therefore possible to strongly recommend the 75% water deficit and therefore apply 75% of the initial Kc as shown in the table below:

Table 1: Potato irrigation recommendations (Kc) for different development stages

Stages	Kc (FAO)	Recommended Kc
Initial	0.45	0.34
Development	0.75	0.56
Mid-season	1.15	0.86
Maturity	0.45	0.56

For onion, the results obtained show that:

(i) 100% ETC irrigation at a threshold of 5% of RAW recorded the maximum bulb diameter and weight, thus achieving the best marketable bulb yields. However, in terms of yields, this treatment is not significantly different from the other irrigation regimes with the exception of the irrigated treatment at 50% daily ETC and at a threshold of 10% RAW. The latter recorded the lowest values in terms of production parameters.

(ii) For the eco-physiological parameters, significant effects of irrigation dose were observed for proline content, stomatal conductance and leaf temperature, and the effect of the triggering threshold was clearly observed for the moisture content of the leaves. (iii) Water restrictions have minimized the rate of premature run and population density of Thrips tabaci in the onion. (iv) Finally, the best agronomic efficiencies in the use of irrigation water were recorded in treatments with a water restriction of 50%.

According to this trial, it is advisable to apply 100 % of water requirements with a triggering threshold of the readily available water content of 5%, if water is not a limiting factor. But, if water is rare, it could be better to apply 75 % of water requirements, saving 25% of irrigation water without having a significant effect on production and quality. Reducing the FAO Kc with 25% is recommended with the condition of a well irrigation scheduling base on the monitoring of soil humidity.

For carrots, the results obtained concerning the total yield show that this parameter is also strongly dependent on the applied water regime. The highest total yield per hectare was recorded in treatment T1 (125%) which was 59.595 T/ha, while the lowest was in treatment T5 (66%) which was 32.417 T/ha.

However, by reducing the water rate by 25%, we still obtained a good yield of 48.7 T/ha, which was not significantly different from the yield of treatment T1. This leads us to say that by saving 25% of the water, we did not affect the yield.

In summary, the results obtained show that irrigation management for different crops allows a significant reduction in irrigation doses, in general the crop coefficients calculated on the basis of optimal irrigation management (doses and frequencies) for the three crops (onion, potatoes, carrots) are lower than those recommended by FAO and allow a reduction of the order of 20-25% in crop water demand for practically equivalent yields (control treatment). This leads us to say

that by saving 20-25% of water, we can achieve optimum yields (good management of irrigation doses).

b. Smart irrigation system (equipment & connectivity)

The main objective is to Develop a specific protocol for the collection, transmission and storage of raw data from IoT sensors using LoRaWAN technology, either using an API for data retrieval on the local server or using a specific protocol.

The installation and testing of the connected sensors in the field was carried out on the experimental trials conducted in spring and summer 2022. (probes, water meters, weather stations, etc.).

The data transmission, via a Gateway installed nearby, was carried out to the Cloud server of the equipment supplier and the information is available on a dedicated proprietary application.

All data collected in the field can be retrieved and loaded on our cloud server or locally based on an API (Application Programming Interface).

The installation and testing of the connected sensors in the field was carried out on the experimental trials conducted in spring and summer 2022. (probes, water counter, weather stations, etc.). The final prototype of the smart irrigation system (small scale) was installed and tested during the vegetables crops season 2023 at the ENAM Experimental Farm. (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Small scale precision irrigation system demonstration unit

(Probes, Weather station, drip system, smart water counter, LoRaWAN transceivers...)

Figure 4: LoRaWAN Gateway for precision agriculture systems installation

The LoRaWAN gateway with solar panels not only makes the IoT infrastructure more resilient and environmentally friendly, but also significantly expands the scope of applications where these systems can be deployed. The costs associated with data exchange with sensors in the field are zero and do not depend on service providers (GPRS, 4/5G)

c. Mobile application for irrigation management

This activity focused on the development of mobile applications integrating data from connected sensors to help manage irrigation doses for the benefit of farmers in the study area. This is an application that calculates, based on data from sensors installed in the field and weather stations, the irrigation needs of the three crops studied. Farmers who do not have sensors in their fields can also benefit from recommendations on irrigation doses for their crops based on data collected in the area of interest at no cost.

The application (EcoMA) interfaces allow to record information on the plot, the crop and its installation date and allows the farmer to obtain recommendations on the irrigation doses continuously until the end of the crop cycle (harvest). The application was distributed and tested during the randomized control tests carried out in mid-2024 with specific training sessions on its use and its different functionalities (200 farmers/400 surveyed).

Figure 5: Screenshots of EcoMa mobile app. for precision irrigation management

2.2.2 Relevant production

Publications, conference abstracts / proceedings / posters, communication articles, news items, ...

- “Comparison of the effectiveness of chameleon sensors and watermark sensors in irrigation scheduling” (Bachelor thesis, Makerere University, Uganda)
- “Design and development of a LoRa communication system for automation of smart irrigation” (Bachelor thesis, Makerere University, Uganda)
- “Precision irrigation for sustainable tomato production in Uganda” (Master thesis, Zurich University for Applied Science, Switzerland)

- “Design and development of a LoRa communication system for scalable smart irrigation systems” “(3rd African Conference on Precision Agriculture, Ruanda)
- Three theses from ENAM engineering students in relation to deficit irrigation for the 3 crops.
- Visit to experimental trials on precision irrigation at the ENAM experimental farm of several groups of farmers and agricultural technicians as part of collaborative activities with the FoodLAND project.
- Presentation of the technological solution (equipment and mobile application) during the International Agricultural Show of Morocco (SIAM 2024) with the collaboration of the Ministry of Agriculture.
- Poster: “Collaborative precision irrigation system for more sustainable agriculture,” Author: Amine Idrissi BEN DAHOU, Nouredine MOKHTARI. Presented at the 16th edition of the International Agricultural Show in Morocco (SIAM) from April 22 to 28, 2024, under the theme “Climate and Agriculture: For sustainable and resilient production systems”.

2.3 Summary of the outcomes

Number of food operators involved in the validation activities (WP5).

Food Hub	Innovation (new technology / system / tool / food product)	n. farmers / SMEs
Nakaseke (UG)	Irrigation trials at Makerere University serving for research of students and farmers	60 students and 40 farmers
Nakaseke (UG)	Chameleon soil moisture sensors are being tested by farmers	3 farmers
Nakaseke (UG)	Farm visits and demonstration of Chameleon soil moisture sensors	11 farmers
Morocco (Ait Ouallal Bittit and Ait Yazem)	Several tests on deficit irrigation were carried out in the ENAM experimental farm and	120 students and over 80 farmers

	served as demonstrations for students and farmers.	
Morocco (Ait Ouallal Bittit and Ait Yazem)	The solution for precision management of irrigation of vegetable crops (onions, potatoes and carrots) is currently being evaluated as part of the RCTs conducted at the zone level. It includes the installation of equipment (sensors and LoRaWAN data transmission system) and the use of the mobile irrigation management application	400 farmers (RCTs)

2.4 Summary of the impacts

Key performance indicators (KPIs: technology, production, nutrition): measures

Food Hub	Innovation (new technology / system / tool / food product)	KPIs measuring the achievements
Nakaseke (UG)	LoRa-based automated irrigation system	Prototype available at Makerere University, field test resulted in 30% yield increase over common irrigation scheduling. Considering the average tomato and production cost ¹ , this translates to a revenue increase of 1'827 USD per hectare of tomato cultivation.
Nakaseke (UG)	Precision deficit irrigation	Tomatoes cultivated under a moderate water deficit resulted in increased sugar (Brix) content and obtained a potential enhanced nutritional value
Morocco (Ait Ouallal Bittit)	Community irrigation consulting platform for small farmers based on precision agriculture techniques	increase of small farmers and SMEs' income by 10%. (by reducing irrigation cost)

¹Assumptions: Average tomato market price in Uganda: 0.59 USD kg⁻¹, production cost: 1 123 USD per hectare of tomato cultivation. Taken from: G. Ddamulira et al. "Practices and constraints of tomato production among smallholder farmers in Uganda". I (June 25, 2021).<https://www.ajol.info/index.php/ajfand/article/view/209460>

Morocco (Ait Ouallal Bittit)	Community irrigation consulting platform for small farmers based on precision agriculture techniques	Reduce irrigation water by 20-25%
Morocco (Ait Ouallal Bittit)	Community irrigation consulting platform for small farmers based on precision agriculture techniques	For carrots crop, improvement in the sugar content (Brix) by 10%

3. Protocol for the implementation

This section adopts an operational perspective to describe how to implement and manage the prototype, thus ensuring its full functionality and usability. It includes the deployment requirements, procedures, methods, techniques, and practical considerations.

3.1 Framework conditions for the prototype

Scope of the prototype, including the general conditions for its implementation, its features, functionalities, and user interactions. This should also specify any limitations or constraints of the prototype.

Nakaseke (UG)

The proposed precision irrigation system is designed to seamlessly integrate into existing irrigation setups, preferable pressurized systems, to improve water efficiency for smallholder farms in Uganda. The system's design prioritizes affordability and local availability of components, enabling farmers to access parts either locally or through international suppliers. However, while components are chosen for local sourcing, acquiring the necessary technical equipment in rural areas may present logistical challenges. In many cases, materials must be sourced from metropolitan areas, such as Kampala, potentially increasing both the cost and complexity of implementation for farmers in remote regions.

The system operates independently of internet infrastructure, relying on local data processing via a Raspberry Pi-based gateway and LoRa communication. This ensures that real-time soil moisture data is transmitted over long distances without requiring internet access. Though for remote control and monitoring using the farmers smartphone internet infrastructure is required. Additionally, the system is safeguarded by a UPS and on the field level powered by solar panels with battery backups, providing a reliable energy source even in areas where electricity supply is unstable. However, prolonged periods of cloudy weather or

power outages could affect the system's performance, making it necessary to monitor power levels regularly.

Despite its autonomous nature, the system does require some degree of technical knowledge for its initial setup, configuration, and ongoing maintenance. Farmers or technicians must be able to install sensors, configure the gateway unit, and align the components properly to ensure optimal operation. Furthermore, the system's irrigation algorithm may need to be adjusted based on specific crop or soil requirements, which involves minor software modifications. This means that farmers must be comfortable with basic technical tasks, including troubleshooting issues related to communication failures, power supply problems, or sensor malfunctions. Adequate training and technical support will be essential to ensure that users can manage and maintain the system effectively.

Another potential limitation is the system's reliance on existing irrigation infrastructure. It assumes that farms already have some form of irrigation setup in place, which may exclude the majority of smallholders in Uganda. Additionally, while the LoRa communication offers reliable long-range data transmission, the effectiveness of the signal can be impacted by geographical obstacles such as hills, dense vegetation, or buildings, which could reduce communication efficiency between the sensor nodes and the gateway unit.

Ait Ouallal Bittit/Ait Yazem (MA)

The intelligent irrigation prototype is designed for for small farmers based on precision agriculture techniques to optimize irrigation conditions. Its implementation requires:

a. Stakeholder Engagement

- **Farmer Involvement:** Active participation of local farmers and cooperatives is crucial for understanding on-ground challenges and ensuring that the platform meets their needs.
- **Partnerships:** Collaboration with local agricultural extension services, research institutions in Agritech Systems to provide expertise and support. (ENAM)
- **Community Buy-In:** Clear communication regarding the benefits of precision irrigation and transparency in operations to foster trust and adoption.

b. Project Management

- **Leadership and Coordination:** Designated project managers or coordinators to oversee development, installation, and ongoing maintenance. (ENAM)
- **Clear Roles & Responsibilities:** Defined roles for technical teams, field technicians, and support staff to ensure accountability and smooth operations.
- **Risk Management:** A proactive risk management plan that identifies potential issues (technical failures, funding gaps, regulatory hurdles) and outlines contingency strategies.

3.1.2. Prototype Features

- **Smart Monitoring System:** IoT-enabled sensors monitor soil moisture, weather conditions, and water flow rate supplied to the crop plot.
- **Data Logging and Analysis:** Continuous recording of environmental parameters to avoid water waste and interact with environmental conditions (climate conditions).
- **User Alerts and Notifications:** Real-time alerts for critical soil moisture changes using a dedicated mobile application.
- **Energy Efficiency:** Optimized operation of sensors and LoRaWAN transmission system to minimize energy consumption while maintaining optimal crop irrigation.

3.1.3. Features

- **Real-time Environmental Monitoring:** Users can check soil moisture and weather statistics to plan irrigation and valve openings via a mobile application.
- **Control of irrigation water valves:** the system can provide information on irrigation duration and frequency according to the crop areas and water flow rates used by the farmer.
- **Predictive analysis:** use of historical data to provide information on irrigation conditions during the crop cycle and potential risks.
- **Maintenance alerts:** notifications for sensor calibration or irrigation system malfunctions (issues related to the efficiency of the irrigation system).

3.1.4. User interactions

- **Farmers and irrigation managers:** access system data, receive alerts and manually adjust irrigation parameters (frequencies and doses to be expected).
- **Technical support staff:** diagnose and resolve sensor malfunctions remotely.

- **Agricultural experts:** analyze the collected data for research and improvement of irrigation techniques.

3.1.5. Limitations and constraints

- **Dependence on connectivity:** the system relies on stable Internet access for LoRaWAN Gateway. The Gateways must therefore be installed in locations with the widest spatial coverage and with Internet connection (mobile telecommunications network) to be able to receive and transfer sensor data to the Cloud for the large area. The coverage must be around 10Km in Diameter to ensure better efficiency of use.
- **Initial configuration costs:** the prototype may require a significant initial investment in the basic infrastructure, Gateways, weather stations and Internet connection. This equipment, once installed, will cover the entire area of interest.
- **Legal authorization:** The use of the LoRaWAN network is subject to prior authorization from the national telecommunications regulatory authorities (ANRT). This procedure for requesting the use of LoRa long-range radio waves must therefore be initiated before the start of installation of the basic infrastructure of the system. Awareness raising on the interest of the technical solution for farmers wishing to implement a smart irrigation system based on the available infrastructure is also important, especially at the beginning of the adoption of the system in order to allow a better diffusion of the innovation.
- **User training:** Good user training is necessary to ensure efficient operation and maintenance of the system and effective use of the mobile application.

3.2 Prerequisites for the prototype / Technical architecture

Technical components and infrastructure necessary to build the prototype, including equipment, inputs and raw materials, personnel, costs, ...

Nakaseke (UG)

Ref.	Requirement description	Priority*
1	Soil moisture sensors (e.g. watermark/chameleon)	M
2	Lora Communication module, for gateway and sensor node	M
3	Raspberry Pi (3/4/5) microcontroller for the gateway	M
4	ESP32 microcontroller for the sensor node	M

5	Interface module for connecting the soil moisture sensors	M
6	Solar panel and backup battery for sensor node	M
7	Actuators like the proposed smart valve or alternately a pump	M
8	Farmers/technicians with basic knowledge of microcontroller setup and maintenance	M
9	Chirpstack open source software for LoRa communication	M
10	USP for the gateway, highly recommended in areas with unstable power supply	1
11	Transport to metropolitan centers (e.g.) Kampala for sourcing of material	2
12	Initial and ongoing training for farmers to operate and troubleshoot the system	2
* Priority: M = mandatory / 1 = high, 2 = medium, 3 = low		

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Ref.	Requirement description	Priority*
1	Equipment and Tools	H
2	Raw Materials and Inputs	H
3	Software components	H
4	Personnel	L
5	Installation Space & Utilities	L
* Priority: M = mandatory / 1 = high, 2 = medium, 3 = low		

3.2.1. Hardware Components (smart irrigation infrastructure)

a. Sensor Nodes

- **Soil Moisture Sensors:** Monitor soil water content.
- **Temperature & Humidity Sensors:** Record ambient environmental conditions.
- **Weather Station:** To provide climate conditions to the system such as rainfall, relative humidity, temperature, radiation, wind speed sensors.
- **Microcontrollers:** Devices such as Arduino, ESP32, or similar low-power microcontrollers to interface with sensors.
- **LoRaWAN Modules:** For wireless communication.

b. Communication Infrastructure

LoRaWAN Gateway with a concentrator board, high-gain antennas to ensure long-range communication and solar panel integration to enable off-grid power for remote locations.

3.2.2. Software Components

a. Cloud & Backend Infrastructure

- **Data Aggregation & Storage:** Cloud platforms to store sensor data.
- **IoT Platform:** Middleware that manages device connectivity, data ingestion (using protocols like MQTT), and processing.
- **Database Systems:** For storing historical sensor data and user information.

b. Mobile and Web Applications

- **Mobile App (Android & iOS): EcoMa (Provided by ENAM) for free** with user interface for irrigation management, receiving irrigation doses recommendations, and viewing sensors data.
- **User Authentication & Data Security:** Secure login and data encryption protocols to ensure privacy and data integrity.

3.2.3. Data Analytics & Decision support

- **Precision Agriculture Algorithms:** Models to analyze sensor data for irrigation recommendations available for three crops (onion, potatoes, carrots): Experimental trials results
- **Reporting & Alert System:** Automated alerts (via SMS or WhatsApp, email, or app notifications) when irrigation adjustments are needed.

3.2.4. Inputs and Raw Materials

- **Software Licenses and Cloud Services:** Subscriptions for cloud hosting, database management, and potential third-party analytics tools.

3.2.5. Personnel Requirements

- **Technicians:** Assist with installation, maintenance, and field testing of hardware
- **Software Developers: Backend Developer:** Maintenance of cloud infrastructure, databases, and APIs and **Mobile App Developer to** Upgrade the mobile application for irrigation management.

3.2.6. Estimated Costs (rough estimate)

Ref.	Component	Cost (Dh)
1	LoRaWAN Network infrastructure, tools and equipment (ENAM)	80000
2	IoT sensors & modules (Farmer)	25000
3	Control System and power supply (Farmer)	2000
4	Miscellaneous (Installation, Testing, Logistics) (Farmer)	1500
	Total	108500

The general conditions of implementation highlight the need for a holistic approach that addresses technical, financial, organizational, regulatory, and environmental factors. Successfully meeting these conditions ensures that the community irrigation consulting platform is not only technically robust but also sustainable, economically viable, and fully aligned with the needs and capabilities of small farmers.

3.3 Implementation

This section outlines the implementation process, including indicative timeline, milestones, and any specific task associated with the innovation adoption.

Nakaseke (UG)

1. Phase 1: Planning and Preparation (Weeks 1-4):
 - Site Selection: Farms selected for the system must be large enough to justify the investment and should focus on high-value crops such as tomatoes, strawberries, or eggplants. Additionally, farms must already have a well-functioning irrigation system and a reliable water source to support the new technology.
 - Component Sourcing: The majority of system components, including sensors, communication modules, and processing units, will be imported from abroad or obtained from suppliers in metropolitan areas like Kampala. The sourcing process, including procurement and handling of import duties, is estimated to take 3-4 weeks.

2. Phase 2: System Installation (Weeks 5-6)
 - Field Setup: Soil moisture sensors will be installed in strategic locations across the farm to monitor moisture levels in real-time. These sensors will be connected to the LoRa sensor node for data transmission. The sensor node is powered by a solar panel and battery

- Gateway Installation: The Raspberry Pi gateway and LoRa concentrator will be installed in the farmer's house or community hub. A UPS module will be included to safeguard the system from power outages.
 - Testing: After installation, a comprehensive testing phase will ensure all components are functioning properly, and the system is transmitting data as expected.
3. Phase 3: Training and Initial Operation (Weeks 7-10)
- Training Program: A training program will be provided to farmers and technicians to equip them with the necessary skills to operate the system. This training will cover topics such as system setup, adjusting the irrigation algorithm, and troubleshooting.
 - Calibration and Fine-Tuning: During training, the system's moisture thresholds and irrigation timing will be calibrated to meet the specific needs of the crops and soil types on the farm.
 - Initial Operation: Once training is complete, the system will enter its initial operational phase, during which an exemplary crop is planted and irrigation will be automated based on real-time data from the soil moisture sensors.
4. Phase 4: Monitoring and Evaluation (Weeks 11 +)
- Performance Monitoring: During the first crop cycle, key performance indicators (KPIs) will be tracked, including:
 - Reduction in water usage
 - Reduction in labor & fertilizer input
 - Increase in crop yield
 - Increase in farm profits
 - Adjustments: Based on the initial monitoring results, the irrigation algorithm or system settings may be adjusted to optimize performance and ensure that the system is delivering the desired results.

Ait Ouallal Bittit/Ait Yazem (MA)

3.3.1. Implementation Phases & Timeline

Phase	Tasks	Timeline	Milestones
Testing & Optimization	- Field deployment, sensors data analysis, system calibration, user feedback collection	8 – 9 months	- Field tests completed, system calibrated and optimized
Deployment and scaling	- Pilot installation, user training, system documentation, establishment of maintenance and support protocols	10-12 months	- Full-scale pilot operational, training completed, support system in place
Adoption	- Development of business model for farmers, marketing, large-scale deployment, continuous R&D and system enhancements	2+ Years	- Market launch, strategic partnerships established, scalability demonstrated continuous R&D and system enhancements

3.3.2. Key Innovation Adoption Tasks

a. Stakeholder Engagement

- **Farmers & Cooperatives:** Demonstrate the benefits of reducing water spoilage and optimizing crops irrigation conditions.
- **Government & Regulators:** Obtain approvals and align with national agricultural policies. (LoRaWAN use, farmer’s organizations, system deployment and sensors installation on the field)

b. Technology Adoption & Training

- **Workshops & Training Sessions:** Educate users on system operation.
- **User-Friendly mobile App:** Ensure accessibility for non-tech-savvy users.
- **Continuous Technical Support:** Establish helplines and troubleshooting guides.

c. Sustainability & Scaling

- **Energy Efficiency Measures:** Develop solar-powered or low-energy consumption battery for sensors in rural areas.
- **Cost Reduction Strategies:** Identify ways to lower hardware and operational costs.
- **Integration with Supply Chains:** Connect with logistics & distribution networks.

3.4 Management

This section outlines any specific aspect or task associated with the management, control, evaluation and maintenance of the implemented innovation.

Nakaseke (UG)

System Control and Data Management

Daily soil moisture data is analyzed to identify any potential outliers, ensuring timely detection of sensor malfunctions or connection or communication issues. On a weekly basis, the irrigation schedule is adjusted to account for the crop's developmental stage and soil moisture response.

Evaluation

The system's performance is reviewed weekly, focusing on water usage, fertilizer application, labor reduction, and crop yield. A more comprehensive evaluation, including technical inspections, is conducted after each crop cycle to assess the overall efficiency and profitability of the system.

Maintenance

After every crop cycle, a full technical check is recommended. This includes inspecting sensors, cable connections, the solar panel effectiveness and battery status. Farmers are encouraged to seek technical support during the first inspection to ensure proper handling and troubleshooting of potential issues.

Ait Ouallal Bittit/Ait Yazem (MA)

3.4.1. Training and Capacity Building:

- **User Training Programs:** Develop comprehensive training sessions (both in-person and digital) to familiarize users with the mobile app and sensor network.
- **Technical Workshops:** Offer periodic workshops for maintenance staff and local technicians to keep them updated on system operations and troubleshooting.

3.4.2. Data Management:

- **Data Governance Policies:** Define clear policies for data collection, storage, privacy, and usage to maintain trust and compliance with regulations.

3.4.3. System Control & Security measures

- **Remote Monitoring and Configuration:** Utilize a central dashboard to monitor real-time sensor data, system health, and network connectivity, allowing for remote reconfiguration as needed.
- **Role-Based Access Control:** Implement user roles (administrator, technician, farmer) with tailored access rights to secure sensitive data and control functions.

3.4.4. Evaluation & Maintenance

a. Performance Metrics and KPIs:

- **System Reliability:** Track uptime, sensor data accuracy, and the frequency of communication outages.
- **Operational Impact:** Measure water usage efficiency, crop yield improvements, and overall resource savings attributable to the platform.
- **User Engagement:** Monitor app usage metrics, active user counts, and feedback scores to gauge farmer satisfaction and adoption levels.

b. Regular Assessments:

- **Periodic Reviews:** Conduct annual evaluations of system performance, including technical audits and user surveys.
- **Data Analytics:** Leverage integrated analytics tools to perform trend analyses, identify bottlenecks, and highlight areas for improvement.

3.4.5. Maintenance

a. Preventive and Routine Maintenance:

- **Scheduled Hardware Inspections:** Develop a routine inspection plan for sensor nodes, gateways, and power systems (solar panels and batteries) to detect wear or potential failures.
- **Sensor Calibration:** Set up regular calibration schedules to ensure sensors maintain accuracy over time, adapting to environmental changes.

b. Software and System Updates:

- **Regular Software Patches:** Implement a maintenance protocol for updating the mobile app, backend servers, and firmware on IoT devices to fix bugs and enhance security.
- **Automated Diagnostics:** Integrate self-diagnostic tools and remote troubleshooting capabilities within the system to promptly identify and address issues.

c. Support and Repair Infrastructure:

- **Technical Support Team:** Establish a dedicated support team for quick response to technical issues, with clear escalation protocols.

4. Conclusions

Final considerations and evaluations including recommendations, possible implications (organizational, operational, policy, ...) and technological improvements, R&I needs and way forward.

The precision irrigation system presents a promising approach for enhancing water efficiency and crop yields on smallholder farms in Uganda. However, for a broad adoption several challenges have to be tackled:

Key Challenges and Recommendations

Financial Constraints: While designed for affordability, the initial investment in imported components can be a significant hurdle for smallholder farmers. Access to subsidies or financing will be necessary to make the system more attainable for rural communities.

Resource Availability: Sourcing critical components by import and from metropolitan areas like Kampala adds logistical challenges, increasing both cost and time. Establishing local supply chains would improve accessibility and reduce costs, making the system more feasible for rural farmers.

Farmer Training: Beyond technical training for system operation and troubleshooting, farmers require agronomic knowledge; in particular an

understanding of water-soil interactions. This deeper knowledge is essential for evaluating and optimizing the irrigation system based on crop and soil needs, ensuring it delivers the expected benefits.

With major detail the following aspects can be underlined:

- **Standards and certifications:**

- **Work with regulators to develop standards for smart irrigation systems that ensure interoperability and security.** Most current commercial solutions are encrypted systems with no possibility of integration, which implies a total dependence of end users (farmers) on service providers for irrigation management.
- **Obtain the necessary permits and certifications,** particularly regarding the installation and deployment of sensors and the use LoRaWAN long range radio frequencies.

- **Incentives and subsidies:**

Advocate for government subsidies or incentives for the integration of digital solutions for irrigation management, particularly for connected capacitive sensors that are relatively expensive on the local market and can hinder the adoption of innovation. This should reduce the financial burden on small farmers who want to adopt precision irrigation technologies. It should be noted that the State currently subsidizes all equipment related to drip irrigation for any type of use in agriculture with a ceiling that can go up to 38.000dh/ha (3600euro), but has not yet provided for the subsidy of digital tools for the efficient management of this equipment. This innovation can be a precursor to encourage public authorities to extend subsidies to digital equipment and installations necessary for the efficient management of drip irrigation networks already benefiting from subsidies.

In this context, a draft law (legislation) is currently being discussed to extend agricultural subsidies to digital tools within the framework of agriculture 4.0. This will make it possible in the near future to take advantage of the financing opportunities offered by subsidies for agro-technological innovations and sustainable agriculture programs financed by the Moroccan State as GGP (Green Generation Program).

- **Possible Implications**

- a. **Organizational Implications**

Transitioning from traditional irrigation (gravity and standard drip irrigation systems) methods to a smart, data-driven system requires significant changes in management practices and organizational culture. Farmers need to find the best way to integrate this technology into the agricultural production system and manage smart tools in the field. (agricultural work in the field should not be disrupted by the installed sensors)

Also, this technology need increased Collaboration and enhanced cooperation between technology providers, farmer's community, local authorities can drive more efficient resource management and improved water usage.

b. Operational Implications

- **Operational Costs:** Although the system can reduce water and labor costs over time. Also, initial setup and periodic maintenance might require significant investment and planning.
- **Improved efficiency with increased complexity:** While automation and real-time analytics can significantly optimize water use and crop health, they also add layers of technical complexity that require skilled maintenance and tool mastery by end users, including calculating and adapting irrigation doses in relation to recommendations provided by the mobile application. (specific training for irrigation precision mastering).

c. Policy and Regulatory Implications

- **Water resources management:** intelligent irrigation systems must align with local water rights (especially with regard to surface water from sources which are managed in a very specific and complex way on the basis of water rights, volume and distribution schedules) and with groundwater resource management policies (pumping authorization) to avoid conflicts and ensure equitable distribution of water.

• Technological Improvements and R&I Needs

a. Technological Improvements

- **Sensor Network Enhancement:** Invest in advanced and more accurate soil moisture, weather, and plant health sensors that offer improved accuracy and durability. Try to integrate multiple communication technologies (e.g., LoRaWAN with backup cellular or satellite connectivity) to ensure robust data transmission.
- **Enhanced Data Analytics and AI:** Develop more sophisticated AI models for predictive analytics that can optimize irrigation scheduling based on weather forecasts, soil conditions, and crop water needs.
- **User Interface and Mobile App Enhancements:** Refine the mobile application and web dashboard to offer intuitive, real-time visualization of irrigation metrics and recommendations. Integrate decision-support tools that translate raw data into actionable insights for farmers and develop local languages interfaces (Arabic, dialect).

• Research and Innovation (R&I) Needs

- **Interdisciplinary Research:** Foster collaborative research between agronomists, sociologies, IoT specialists, data scientists, and policy experts to address the unique challenges of precision irrigation.
- **Cost Reduction and Scalability:** Research cost-effective solutions for mass production and deployment to make the system accessible to a broader range of small farmers (irrigation probe sensors, connectivity system...)

• Way Forward

The system should be extensively tested in real-world conditions across diverse locations to evaluate its practicality and robustness. These tests will provide valuable insights into how the system performs under varying environmental conditions. Based on the results, improvements can be made to material selection and software interfaces, enhancing both durability and user interaction. These refinements will make the system more user-friendly and reliable, ultimately driving its broader adoption.

- **In Short-Term (1-2 Years):** Conduct training and Awareness: Launch targeted training programs and awareness campaigns to educate farmers on the benefits of smart irrigation.
- **Medium-Term (3-5 Years):** System Scaling and Integration: Scale the system to cover larger geographical areas and integrate with broader water management networks and enhance the system's analytics capabilities to incorporate more complex models and real-time decision support.
- **Long-Term (5+ Years):** Adapt system to full Autonomy and Advanced Integration: Transition to a fully autonomous smart irrigation ecosystem that minimizes manual intervention and costs.

The smart irrigation system represents a transformative approach to water management in agriculture in the area, offering substantial benefits in terms of efficiency, sustainability, and crop productivity. By addressing key organizational, operational, and policy considerations, and by investing in continuous technological improvements and interdisciplinary R&I, the system can meet the evolving needs of small farmers. The way forward involves iterative optimization, strategic scaling, and proactive policy engagement to ensure that the smart irrigation system remains robust, user-friendly, and capable of driving sustainable agricultural practices.

